

IMPACT OF TENNIS ON THE HUMAN BODY: SCIENTIFIC LITERATURE
ANALYSIS OF DATA

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Abstract. The article describes such a sport as tennis. Its influence on the human body is considered. Tennis helps to keep almost all muscle groups in good shape, develops the respiratory and cardiac systems well, improves the functioning of the circulatory system and the flow of oxygen, but, what is also important, it strengthens endurance, “hardens” a person.

Keywords: tennis, respiratory system, cardiovascular system, body, dynamics, movement, intelligence, endorphins, hypertonicity, cardio training.

Introduction. Tennis has been one of the most popular sports for decades. Tennis is practiced by millions of people around the world, it is suitable for adults and children, professionals and amateurs. Many people leading a healthy lifestyle prefer this particular sport, as it has a positive effect not only on physical health, but also on psychological health, giving a person a lot of positive emotions. Tennis develops not only the body, but also helps personal growth, educating character and discipline. It is impossible to underestimate the benefits of tennis on the human body. The game really has a great impact on the athlete and not only helps to stay in good shape. In addition to physical activity, tennis, as they say, teaches "logic". No wonder this sport is referred to as "intellectual". Therefore, the question of what develops tennis cannot be limited only to the answer that tennis develops muscle groups. Not the last role in the game is given to the strategy and tactics of each game, the calculation of the pros and cons of the opponent, the forecast of his moves, and so on. And although tennis is one of the safest sports, misses are possible.

Research results and their discussion. What develops tennis? Let's talk about this sport in as much detail as possible. Let's start with the muscles and body systems that this

game develops. Much of the work done by the muscles in tennis is dynamic. As a rule, this manifests itself in concentric and eccentric movements. A lot of movements and techniques in tennis lead to contraction and lengthening of muscle fibers. It turns out that during the game one muscle group is constantly working to accelerate movements, the second, on the contrary, to slow down. Of course, since an athlete works with a racket all the time, one of the main muscle groups involved in the process is biceps and triceps. An important role is given to the muscles of the legs, which are also constantly tense and require sudden movements, the search for balance, and so on. In general, tennis is just one of those sports in which all muscle groups are fairly evenly involved, and this, of course, makes this hobby indispensable for those who want to relieve stress after a busy work schedule and keep themselves in shape. But for this, the loads must be dosed and regular. In addition to dynamic movements, tennis is characterized by static ones, and this is the work of a different muscle group and according to a different principle. The muscles of the back, neck, abs and others - everything really works in tennis!

Tennis, as already noted, has a positive effect on the relaxation of muscles that are in a state of hypertonicity. In addition, with strong, consistent, frequent muscle tension, the production of endorphins occurs, and this, as we know, is the hormones of happiness, which have a beneficial effect on the body and even prolong life. During the game, the respiratory and cardiovascular systems are trained. Tennis is generally the perfect cardio workout . Tennis is useful not only from the side of anatomy, but also psychology - the game helps to relieve not only muscular, but also emotional stress. Due to the increased concentration in the process, after - there is a sharp relaxation, this is a change of states and gives its healing effect. The processes of the birth of new nerve cells are accelerated, the reaction and coordination are improved. Assertiveness, energy, improved memory and thinking - all this is also inherent in people involved in tennis. Tennis improves the ability of your brain. It stimulates the brain to be creative and fast. Thus, the longer you play tennis, the better and stronger the neural connections in your brain associated with these activities become, and the better you become at them. Research shows that in addition to improving neural connections and the emergence of new neurons, sports that require a lot of thinking, and this is just about tennis (calculating steps forward, strategizing the game) can actually improve

brain function by helping memory, learning, social skills and anxious, angry and depressed than people who play other sports or lead a sedentary lifestyle, according to Connecticut scientists .

Benefits of tennis:

- Tennis has a positive effect on the functioning of the cardiovascular system.
- It develops the respiratory system, which increases the supply of oxygen to all organs and systems of the body.
- Tennis, like other types of physical activity, helps to strengthen the immune system, hardens the body, makes it more resilient, and improves overall health.
- This sport helps to cope with physical and psychological stress, has a positive effect on the nervous system, helps to cope with stress and depression.
- During tennis practice, almost all muscle groups are involved. This allows you to form a beautiful harmoniously developed figure without resorting to various exercises and exercises on several simulators to work out different muscle groups.
- Regular practice of tennis helps to solve the problem of excess weight.
- This sport disciplines a person, develops attention and increases reaction speed.

Benefits of playing tennis for children:

- No contact. Collision and contact sports have been the cause of the lifelong injuries they can cause over the years. While tennis isn't without its fair share of accidents - if you've played long enough, you've been hit with a tennis ball multiple times - racquet sports have certainly become a favorable option for parents looking for a safe and healthy sport for their child.
- Physical development. A great way to tire your little one out, playing tennis involves a lot of running, quick movements, and using your whole body. As a result, the development of muscular strength of the body is inevitable. Combine this with strengthening the cardiovascular system.
- Mental development. Because tennis requires vigilance and tactical thinking, tennis can create “new connections between nerves in the brain, promoting lifelong brain development,” according to scientists at the University of Illinois. It is also an effective sport for mastering fine motor skills and coordination.

- It is a social and fun sport. We could go on and on about the health and safety benefits of playing tennis, but above all, we truly believe that when it comes to any sport, it should start with fun. An ingrained history of good sportsmanship, teamwork and camaraderie among the players, tennis has always been a social sport that results in enjoyment. Plus, fresh air doesn't hurt!

Conclusion. Tennis is one of the safest sports today. This feature of tennis helps us in the formation of a healthy lifestyle. It is necessary to turn tennis into a mass sport. Because its benefits for the body are countless, and playing tennis is much safer than other sports. More people should be involved in this sport , because it is through this sport that we can form a safe and healthy lifestyle. Tennis shapes a person not only physically and spiritually, but also mentally. Tennis is called an intellectual sport for a reason.

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